

Participatory tools

BASIC TOOLS TO BEGIN IN FACILITATION

Some tools are very common and straightforward, like sticky notes, votes, brainstorming, etc. A beginner facilitator can start by using these tools to gain confidence and practice. Those tools can also be used with participants who are not used to participatory meetings. Being active in a meeting and speaking freely in front of a group can be scary if not in your work habits. To facilitate the process, the facilitator chooses simple tools to explain, understand and implement.

Examples of basic tools to begin in facilitation

Sticky-dots vote – You don't need to do the big voice. Stickers have the same weight.

Description of the tool

- **What:** prioritise, prioritise elements, choose the following topics to work on
- **How long:** 15 to 20 min
- **How many:** max about 15
- **What you'll need:** sticky dots

Steps:

- This step follows a production step or the presentation of the voting elements. The facilitator makes sure that the elements to be prioritised are clear to everyone.
- The facilitator distributes the stickers and gives instructions. For example, they can vary according to the objective (one or X stickers per participant, stickers of different colours to show interest or not).
- Let the participants circulate and stick the stickers.
- The facilitator summarises the results, asks for clarification (if necessary) and validates with the group.

Tips

- Logistic:
 - Cut out the sticker roll with the number of stickers per participant beforehand to save time
 - Think about where to stick the stickers
 - Leave space to read/paste and move around
 - Number of stickers to think about and distribute evenly

LIAISON Interactive guide to facilitating participatory projects

- To help the participants:
 - Simple and straightforward rules of the game in the way decisions are made at the end
 - Sound synthesis for proposals at the beginning

The Fridge – Elegant and efficient handling of questions and interruptions

Description of the tool

- What: How to listen to different opinions and questions while remaining focused on a goal? There is a simple way, "the fridge".
- How long: immediate, spontaneous use
- How many: no limit
- What you'll need: A free space (board, white sheet) is set up in the room or on the shared work screen (virtual board)

Steps:

- At the beginning of the meeting, the facilitator mentions the existence of the fridge and the fact that everyone can come and put their ideas in it whenever they want.

Testimony of the use

Marleen Gysen, ISP, Belgium

During the interview, Marleen Gysen said: "I have been using this tool again recently. I really like it. I find it very effective. It is "a simple method, useful everywhere! It

really helped me with a group of farmers who had a lot of questions. I used the fridge to keep the discussion going while listening to their requests. It's often a challenge to do these two things at odds. It builds trust and calms the group. Plus, we get to listen to each other better."

Tips

Remember to value what is written; otherwise, it is counterproductive, leading to a loss of confidence.

More tools:

[Group work](#)

[Brainstorm](#)

